

How Music does affect Memory

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2017

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How does music affect memory?

Abstract

How would you would feel when you would come to know that you can increase your memory or learning skills with the help of music. The research was conducted under the research question of how does music affects human memory. Participants were taken and given a questionnaire having several different questions. Responses were taken which gives the results that yes music do have effect on memory. The place where background music is being played helps one to relax their mind and body. Basically it is a tension reliever because by listening to music dopamine is released in our body which is a feel good hormone. And thus a relaxed mind can do work with more efficiency. Music can cast anyone into any mood. So the choice of your music is also much related with your personality as well. With the help of musical notes and rhythm one can easily learn other languages as well which are foreign to them. It has been seen that music also affects mood as well. There are three types of memory and memory on basic level is the retention of sensory information. Music even effects a baby which is present I n the womb of mother. Music has much importance in entertainment like in TV and film industry. The etymology of music goes back to the Greek word “mousike” which is derived from “muses” the Greek goddess of art. Einstein became good at study by the influence of music. Kids of kindergarten are taught alphabets in a tune so that they could remember that easily, music is very much important aspect of our lives plus it also has great and positive influence on memory.

Keywords: memory, learning, choice, effect

Research is about music and memory or how they are related with each other. Music does have impacts on the human memory. Memory, on basic level, is considered a way of remembering different things but on higher level it should be regarded as a process of gaining

things from different sources and synthesizing them in multiple forms; in simple words, memory is the ability of mind to save, store, remember, and retrieve information (Bernie. C). When we talk about memory well it is the basic process of retaining the sensory information stored in brain. On the other hand Merriam Webster (2018) defines music as the relationship between the different sounds in a harmonic way so that, that may sounds good. The researcher is much interested into this research because of his musical talent or he has seen music affecting memory he has some personal experiences as well another reason of selecting this topic is that researcher is much interested in music as he himself plays several musical instruments. He wants to see whether music affects human memory or not. The relation between music and memory what researcher has seen and observed is that music affect memory to be retrieved easily or it makes everyone remember things easily. Some researchers have concluded that music aids to memory like if one is learning in background music, his mind would tend to interrelate the musical sound with that learning and when the same music would be played that learning is more likely to come to mind early. The significance and scope of the topic is very diverse as it is said that the music is the food of soul and it is also considered as universal language of humanity (Schopenhauer. A) so the researcher felt great need to conduct a research on impacts of music on memory and to show the value of music. Moreover musicians have good coordination in their brain and other body parts, like for instance a drummer plays drums with both hands and feet similarly a pianist have good coordination between his both hands even when he has to play different notes with both hands. Research might help those who have difficulty is learning things easily. It can help students to learn and remember faster from the results of this research people can improve their learning skills. Listening tastes might be different but the music is listened by most of people. To

make people realize that what wonders music can do, if used sensibly, this research is being conducted. The researcher suggests a question here;

How does music affect human memory?

Literature review

Memory, on basic level, is considered a way of remembering different things but on higher level it should be regarded as a process of gaining things from different sources and synthesizing them in multiple forms in simple words memory is the ability of mind to save store, remember and retrieve information(Bernie. C). There are three types of memory first one is sensory memory which lasts less than a second, second one is short term memory which is also known as working memory lasts for less than a minute, then comes the third type which is called as long term memory it might last for life time (Mastin, L 2010) .There are many types of music as well, few are Jazz, pop, classical, hip-hop and many others. Music affects personalities basically it moulds the personality of people (Bolek, Brown, Gulley, Kenney, Munn, Ross, & Sayers, 2008). It has been seen also that when a baby when he is inside the mother's womb can hears the music and when he hears the same music he shows response it is because of the musical notes which he remembers (Macrae 2016). Music basically is the words that are expressed in the form of rhythm, beat and tempo. It also leaves an impact on its listener. It has been the part of human life since ages. According to Olga Samaroff Stokowski (1935),” Music, similar to nature, has generally varying appearances. It has been utilized as a part of association with religion, wonderful content, show and the move. It has served to propose, depict or delineate things that are unfamiliar to it”(194). For most of the people music is a remedy for relief of stress as well.

Music has become so much popular nowadays. If I say that it's hard to think about a life without music is difficult, would be 100% correct. "On the bad news side, studies have shown that some types of music can result in deleterious effects to the mind and body"(Taylor.A). Music affects one's personality in many ways. First of all the type of music he/she likes becomes the representative of their personality. For instance it has become a stereotype that a boring or conservative type of person would like classical (although it has no scientific proof but still it do exist). If a person having very firm attitude for example a person having lot of ego, would be considered as liking hard rock type of music. In this way music has been coined with the personalities of people. Young children can be sent to sleep by making them listen to the lullabies. We have seen that the songs sung during the Christmas time are so joyful but the songs of Good Friday and funerals are sad, and the tunes are also such types which would put you in a down mood condition. Music play a vital role in film industry as well, for instance the musical background of suspense is such chosen in order to shock the spectators. Background music also plays a major role in any type of electronic entertainment. It can make you fall asleep, it can cause you happiness or sadness, and it can cast you in any mood.

In order to know more deeply about music and its relation with human memory, we need to know about its brief history. According to Wikipedia The word of music is derived from Greek word "mousy" that is derived from another Greek word "mouse" or it might be derived from Greek word "mousike" which is derived from "muses" the Greek goddess of arts. There are many people who have defined music in various ways, like Thomas Clifton (1983) defines music as "measured and specific ordered arrangements of silence and sounds"

Everyone must have noticed that we learn the lyrics of a song fast, but we find it difficult to learn lessons it is all because of music. It affects our memory beyond our thinking.

“Albert Einstein was not so good in studies even his parents were requested to take him away, but instead of doing that his parents brought him a violin and he became good in that. Albert Einstein was greatest thinker and intellectual person of last century, same as Thomas Jefferson while writing Declaration of independence used his violin, when it was difficult for him to choose right words” (O'Donnell 1999). According to Bates and Ferri (2010) in every culture or in every era of time people wanted entertainment and music is a form of entertainment. It entertains us and helps us to relax as well. William R. Klemm (2013) suggested that the act of listening to music is pleasurable because when someone listens to music Dopamine is released is “feel good” neurotransmitter, and when someone is feeling good he is more likely to remember things, as dopamine promotes learning to get rewards, and deficiency of it prepare the one for punishment. Rhythmic track appeals extra after the thoughts yet makes its listeners more passionate. Impacts regarding the brain concerning prolonged publicity according to electric manifestation regarding rhythmic tune is comparable after so on drugs. (Hegarty, 2018)

A famed Bulgarian psychologist, Dr. George Lozanov, designed a way to educate foreign languages in a fragment of the ordinary getting to know time. The usage of his device, students could study up to one half of the vocabulary and terms for the entire school time period (which quantities to nearly 1,000 phrases or terms) in one day. In conjunction with this, the common retention fee of his students becomes 92%. Dr. Lozanov's device concerned the usage of certain classical tune pieces from the baroque length that have around a 60 beats in keeping with minute pattern. He has tested that foreign languages may be learned with 85-one hundred% performance in most effective thirty days by way of the use of these baroque portions. His students had a keep

in mind accuracy charge of almost a hundred percent even after not reviewing the fabric for 4 years.

Kids of kindergarten are taught alphabets of English in a rhythm so that they can remember them and retrieve them easily, might be the same reason implies to the fact that why couldn't we remember Urdu alphabets easily.

Method

Total number of participants was 38 and the selection of participants was random, majority of them were males. All participants volunteered to take part in this survey. No money or any kind of benefit was given to them. A questionnaire was made and sent by mail and was shared on social media to several people and they all were requested by the researcher to fill it. No response was taken in hard copy. No restriction was made in selection and participation of participants. All participants were assigned same question paper. The questionnaire had 16 questions few of them were of yes no type but others were not having several options dealing with music, its types and its impacts on memory. Many questions were related directly to music and memory but many others were also related indirectly with the topic of concern in order to get honest opinion. All participants were Pakistanis, belonging to Muslim and Christian religious backgrounds.

Findings

Mostly young people participated in this research mostly were of range almost 18 to 26 years. In which almost more than half were male and day scholar. When they were asked how often do they listen music the answer which most of them gave was very often or quite often that answer covered more than half of all answers. When participants were asked to give their opinion on would they like to study at a place where background music being played so in this

regard 67% people said may be or yes in addition to it again more than half consider listening music helps to memorize things easily. Further when they were asked that when you listen to a song after a year or two, do it yield same type of emotions as it used to do before, then the response was in favor of stance 58% participants said yes and 25% said may be, but besides this when the participants was asked that if they have to give an exam where background music is being played then the answer was quite shocking more than half almost 61% said they would be distracted and 30.6% people said they would be having no effect while only 8.3% people said they would be more focused. After this, all were asked whether they remember childhood poems or rhymes or not, in which the answer was predictable almost 90% said yes and when they were asked what could be the possible reason behind it then half of them said music cause it to be in my mind. Finally when they were asked that according to them music improves memory then almost 80% of them gave their opinions as strongly agree, slightly agree and neutral.

So according to you music improves memory.

(Generated by Google forms)

Discussion

In the last question of questionnaire the researcher asked the participants that according to them music affects memory or not, in which 80% said strongly agree, slightly agree, and may be, which gives a clear indication that somehow or the other music have effect on memory. If we teach children the alphabets of English without rhythm or music then it would be difficult for them to memorize or remember. It has also found that music put good effects to memory like Einstein was weak in studies but once he started plating violin it became easily for him to remember things easily. Other side of it is that listening to music helps one to relax by producing dopamine and a relaxed mind would remember things more efficiently.

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Appendix

MUSIC AND MEMORY

This questionnaire attempts to acquire your opinion on how music affects memory. Your honest opinion is highly valuable. I would be very thank you for your effort and precious time.

Age

Your answer _____

Gender

Female

Male

Major

Your answer _____

Are you a day scholar?

Yes

No

How often do you listen to music?

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Quite often

Very often

At what time do you usually study?

Morning

Afternoon

Evening

One a scale from 1 -5 where 1 is the lowest and 5 is the highest, rank the subsequent forms of music.

	1	2	3	4	5
Classical	☐				
Rap/Pop	☐				
Rock	☐				
Traditional	☐				

Evaluate the following

	Strongly disagree	disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Listening to music helps you to remember things easily	☐				
With the help of background music you would learn to retrieve memory easily.	☐				
You personally use songs or rhythms to prepare for examinations.	☐				

Usually I listen to music

- While doing homework
- While studying for a test
- While studying for a quiz
- None of the above

Would you like to study at a place where background music is being played?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

During exam if there is background music then you would be

- Distracted
- More focused
- Having no effect

Do you think that listening to music helps you to memorize or learn things easily

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

When you listen to a song after a year or two, do it yield same type of emotions as it did before.

- Yes
- No
- May be
- I don't know

Do you still remember some childhood rhymes and poems?

- Yes
- No

If yes then what could be the reason behind it according to you?

- Music cause it to be in my mind
- Being a child one have a better remembering capability
- I don't know

So according to you music improves memory.

- Strongly agree
- slightly agree
- Neutral
- Slightly disagree
- Strongly disagree

SUBMIT

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Link to the form is below:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfe6Oaz1OmYi9JzbTzWBvm5-uvGjO9aS6GnYLMdUL1EwpniKA/viewform?usp=sf_link